

A Study on Tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer Fractional Operator

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Abstract

This paper introduces novel definitions of the tempered (k, ψ) -fractional operators and establishes their various properties. Our research focuses on applying these new findings to investigate the existence and uniqueness of solutions for a specific class of initial value problems concerning implicit nonlinear fractional differential equations and tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer fractional derivative with nonlocal condition. To achieve this, we rely on the application of pertinent fixed-point theorems. Moreover, we offer illustrative examples to showcase the practical effectiveness of our main results.

Keywords: ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative, k -generalized ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative, tempered fractional operators, existence, uniqueness.

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1. Introduction

Fractional calculus, an intriguing approach that extends differentiation and integration to non-integer orders, has garnered significant attention in both theoretical studies and practical applications across diverse research domains. Its versatility in addressing intricate problems has established it as a crucial tool in the field. Recent years have witnessed a remarkable surge in research on fractional calculus, with authors

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exploring diverse outcomes under varying conditions and forms of fractional differential equations and inclusions. For more details on the applications of fractional calculus, the reader is directed to the books of Herrmann [14], Hilfer [15], Kilbas *et al.* [16] and Samko *et al.* [37]. Agrawal [2] introduced some generalizations of fractional integrals and derivatives and presented some of their properties. In [5, 6], Benchohra *et al.* demonstrated the existence, uniqueness, and stability results for various classes of problems with different conditions with some form of extension of the well-known Hilfer fractional derivative which unifies the Riemann-Liouville and Caputo fractional derivatives.

In a recent publication [11], Diaz introduced novel definitions for the special functions k -gamma and k -beta. To delve deeper into this topic, interested readers can refer to additional sources such as [24, 10, 25]. Furthermore, in another work [41], Sousa *et al.* presented the ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative with respect to another function and elucidated some crucial properties related to this type of fractional operators. For further insights and more results based on this operator, we suggest exploring the papers [1, 39, 40, 3] and their respective reference lists. Drawing inspiration from the various papers cited earlier, we have introduced a novel extension of the renowned Hilfer fractional derivative [36]. This new extension, referred to as the k -generalized ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative, has allowed us to establish a generalization of Grönwall's lemma and explore several types of Ulam stability. Furthermore, we have conducted an in-depth investigation of qualitative and quantitative results for diverse classes of fractional differential problems [17, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34, 35], all made possible through the application of this new generalized fractional operator. See [5, 6], for more details.

In recent years, tempered fractional calculus has emerged as a noteworthy class of fractional calculus operators. It is capable of generalizing various forms of fractional calculus and possesses analytic kernels. This class is viewed as an extension of fractional calculus since it can describe the transition between normal and anomalous diffusion. The definitions of fractional integration with weak singular and exponential kernels were established by Buschman's seminal work [8], and further elaboration on this topic can be found in [20, 28, 38, 26, 4, 23]. Even though the Caputo tempered fractional derivative has not received much attention in the literature, it has the potential to make a substantial contribution to this discipline. By studying the Caputo tempered fractional derivative, we aim to gain a better understanding of its properties and potential applications in this unique mathematical notion. Through this study, we hope to contribute to the advancement of fractional calculus. In their work cited as [22], Kucche *et al.* made a significant advancement in the field of tempered fractional integrals and derivatives. They not only introduced a new framework for calculating these integrals and derivatives but also presented a comprehensive set of properties and results related to this theory. Continuing their research, the same team extended the theory in their subsequent work referenced as [19]. In this continuation, they delved further into the topic of tempered fractional calculus with respect to functions, introducing the tempered Hilfer-type operator. Based on the research conducted in previous studies and employing the k -gamma and k -beta functions along with their properties from [11], we present a novel definition for the tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer fractional operator. Furthermore, we thoroughly analyze the properties of this operator. We believe that this operator serves as a natural extension, enriching the current framework and offering valuable insights for exploring applications of tempered fractional calculus concerning functions. Additionally, it opens up promising opportunities for future research in this dynamic and evolving field.

Nonlocal conditions were introduced by Byszewski [9] to establish the existence and uniqueness of mild and classical solutions for nonlocal Cauchy problems. These nonlocal conditions offer a more effective description of certain physical phenomena compared to standard initial conditions. The study of fractional differential equations with nonlocal conditions can be found in [7, 12, 21, 42, 29] and related references. Nonlocal conditions frequently arise in applications and can be viewed as feedback controls in mathematical models, ensuring that a qualitative feature or magnitude of the solution aligns with its original state during its evolution.

In [18], the authors considered a class of problems for nonlinear Caputo tempered implicit fractional differential equations with boundary conditions and delay:

$$\begin{cases} {}_0^C D_t^{\beta,\gamma} x(t) = \Psi \left(t, x_t, {}_0^C D_t^{\beta,\gamma} x(t) \right), & t \in \Xi := [0, \varkappa], \\ x(t) = \Lambda(t), & t \in [-\kappa, 0], \\ \delta_1 x(0) + \delta_2 x(\varkappa) = \delta_3, \end{cases}$$

where $0 < \beta < 1, \gamma \geq 0$, ${}_0^C D_t^{\beta,\gamma}$ is the Caputo tempered fractional derivative, $\Psi : \Xi \times C([-\kappa, 0], \mathbb{R}) \times \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function, $x \in C([-\kappa, 0], \mathbb{R})$, $0 < \varkappa < +\infty$, $\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3$ are real constants, and $\kappa > 0$ is the time delay. Their arguments are based on Banach, Schauder and Schaefer fixed point theorems.

In [36], the authors considered the initial value problem with nonlinear implicit k -generalized ψ -Hilfer type fractional differential equation:

$$\begin{cases} \left({}_k^H \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r;\psi} x \right) (t) = f \left(t, x(t), \left({}_k^H \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r;\psi} x \right) (t) \right), & t \in (a, b], \\ \left(\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi} x \right) (a^+) = x_0, \end{cases}$$

where ${}_k^H \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r;\psi}$, $\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi}$ are the k -generalized ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative of order $\vartheta \in (0, 1)$ and type $r \in [0, 1]$, and k -generalized ψ -fractional integral of order $k(1 - \xi)$ respectively, where $\xi = \frac{1}{k}(r(k - \vartheta) + \vartheta)$, $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$, $k > 0$ and $f \in C([a, b] \times \mathbb{R}^2, \mathbb{R})$.

In order to generalize our prior results, in this paper, we establish existence and uniqueness results to the following tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer initial value problem with nonlinear implicit fractional differential equation:

$$\left({}_k^{TH} \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} x \right) (t) = f \left(t, x(t), \left({}_k^{TH} \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} x \right) (t) \right), \quad t \in (a, b], \tag{1.1}$$

$$\left({}_\lambda^T \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi} x \right) (a^+) = x_0, \tag{1.2}$$

where ${}_k^{TH} \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi}$, ${}_\lambda^T \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi}$ are the tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer fractional derivative of order $\vartheta \in (0, k)$, $r \in [0, 1]$ and index $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, and tempered (k, ψ) -fractional integral of order $k(1 - \xi)$ and index λ defined in Section 2 respectively, where $\xi = \frac{1}{k}(r(k - \vartheta) + \vartheta)$, $k > 0$, $x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$, $f : [a, b] \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a given appropriate function specified later.

Next, we consider the following nonlocal problem:

$$\left({}_k^{TH} \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} x \right) (t) = f \left(t, x(t), \left({}_k^{TH} \mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} x \right) (t) \right), \quad t \in (a, b], \tag{1.3}$$

$$\left({}_\lambda^T \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi} x \right) (a^+) + \Phi(x) = x_0, \tag{1.4}$$

where $\Phi : C_{\xi;\psi}(J) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function specified later.

This paper has the following structure: Section 2 begins by introducing the necessary notations and providing a review of some preliminaries related to k -generalized ψ -Hilfer and tempered fractional operators, along with the functions k -Gamma, k -Beta, and several auxiliary results. Further, we give the definition of the tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer fractional derivative and some essential theorems and lemmas. In Section 3, we present an existence and uniqueness result for the problem (1.1)-(1.2) that is founded on the Banach contraction principle. In Section 4, we consider an existence result of the nonlocal problem (1.3)-(1.4) that is based on Schaefer’s fixed point theorem. Finally, the last section is dedicated to providing illustrative examples that effectively showcase the practical applicability of our main findings.

2. Preliminaries

First, we present the weighted spaces, notations, definitions, and preliminary facts which are used in this paper. Let $0 < a < b < \infty$, $J = [a, b]$, $\vartheta \in (0, k)$, $r \in [0, 1]$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, $k > 0$ and $\xi = \frac{1}{k}(r(k - \vartheta) + \vartheta)$. By $C(J, \mathbb{R})$ we denote the Banach space of all continuous functions from J into \mathbb{R} with the norm

$$\|x\|_\infty = \sup\{|x(t)| : t \in J\}.$$

$AC^n(J, \mathbb{R})$, $C^n(J, \mathbb{R})$ be the spaces of continuous functions, n -times absolutely continuous and n -times continuously differentiable functions on J , respectively.

Consider the weighted Banach space

$$C_{\xi;\psi}(J) = \left\{ x : (a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : t \rightarrow \Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a)x(t) \in C(J, \mathbb{R}) \right\},$$

where $\Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a) = (\psi(t) - \psi(a))^{1-\xi}$, with the norm

$$\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} = \sup_{t \in [a, b]} \left| \Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a)x(t) \right|,$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} C_{\xi;\psi}^n(J) &= \left\{ x \in C^{n-1}(J, \mathbb{R}) : x^{(n)} \in C_{\xi;\psi}(J) \right\}, n \in \mathbb{N}, \\ C_{\xi;\psi}^0(J) &= C_{\xi;\psi}(J), \end{aligned}$$

with the norm

$$\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}^n} = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \|x^{(i)}\|_\infty + \|x^{(n)}\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}}.$$

Consider the space $X_\psi^p(a, b)$, ($c \in \mathbb{R}$, $1 \leq p \leq \infty$) of those real-valued Lebesgue measurable functions g on $[a, b]$ for which $\|g\|_{X_\psi^p} < \infty$, where the norm is defined by

$$\|g\|_{X_\psi^p} = \left(\int_a^b \psi'(t)|g(t)|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}},$$

where ψ is an increasing and positive function on $[a, b]$ such that ψ' is continuous on $[a, b]$ with $\psi(0) = 0$. In particular, when $\psi(x) = x$, the space $X_\psi^p(a, b)$ coincides with the $L_p(a, b)$ space.

Definition 2.1 ([11]). The k -gamma function is defined by

$$\Gamma_k(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{t^k}{k}} dt, \alpha > 0.$$

When $k \rightarrow 1$ then $\Gamma_k(\alpha) \rightarrow \Gamma(\alpha)$, we have also some useful following relations $\Gamma_k(\alpha) = k^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha}{k}\right)$, $\Gamma_k(\alpha + k) = \alpha \Gamma_k(\alpha)$ and $\Gamma_k(k) = \Gamma(1) = 1$. Furthermore k -beta function is defined as follows

$$B_k(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{k} \int_0^1 t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} (1-t)^{\frac{\beta}{k}-1} dt$$

so that $B_k(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{k} B\left(\frac{\alpha}{k}, \frac{\beta}{k}\right)$ and $B_k(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{\Gamma_k(\alpha)\Gamma_k(\beta)}{\Gamma_k(\alpha+\beta)}$.

2.1. *Fractional Integrals*

Now, we give all the definitions to the different fractional integrals used throughout this paper.

Definition 2.2 (*k*-Generalized ψ -fractional Integral [27]). Let $g \in X_\psi^p(a, b)$ and $[a, b]$ be a finite or infinite interval on the real axis $\mathbb{R} = (-\infty, \infty)$, $\psi(t) > 0$ be an increasing function on (a, b) and $\psi'(t) > 0$ be continuous on (a, b) and $\vartheta > 0$. The generalized *k*-fractional integral operators of a function g (left-sided and right-sided) of order ϑ are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} g(t) &= \int_a^t \bar{\Psi}_\vartheta^{k, \psi}(t, s) \psi'(s) g(s) ds, \\ \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} g(t) &= \int_t^b \bar{\Psi}_\vartheta^{k, \psi}(s, t) \psi'(s) g(s) ds, \end{aligned}$$

with $k > 0$ and $\bar{\Psi}_\vartheta^{k, \psi}(t, s) = \frac{(\psi(t) - \psi(s))^{\frac{\vartheta}{k} - 1}}{k\Gamma_k(\vartheta)}$.

Also in [25], Nápoles Valdés gave a more generalized fractional integral operators defined by

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_{G, a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} g(t) &= \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\vartheta)} \int_a^t \frac{\psi'(s) g(s) ds}{G(\psi(t) - \psi(s), \frac{\vartheta}{k})}, \\ \mathcal{J}_{G, b^-}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} g(t) &= \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\vartheta)} \int_t^b \frac{\psi'(s) g(s) ds}{G(\psi(s) - \psi(t), \frac{\vartheta}{k})}, \end{aligned}$$

where $G(z, \vartheta) \in AC[a, b]$; the space of absolutely continuous functions defined on $[a, b]$.

Definition 2.3 (The ψ -tempered fractional Integral [22]). Let $g \in X_\psi^p(a, b)$ and $[a, b]$ be a finite or infinite interval on the real axis $\mathbb{R} = (-\infty, \infty)$, $\psi(t) > 0$ be an increasing function on (a, b) and $\psi'(t) > 0$ be continuous on (a, b) , $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\vartheta > 0$. The ψ -tempered fractional integral operators of a function g (left-sided and right-sided) of order ϑ and index λ are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} {}_T^\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta; \psi} g(t) &= \int_a^t \frac{(\psi(t) - \psi(s))^{\vartheta - 1}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} e^{-\lambda(\psi(t) - \psi(s))} \psi'(s) g(s) ds, \\ {}_T^\lambda \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{\vartheta; \psi} g(t) &= \int_t^b \frac{(\psi(s) - \psi(t))^{\vartheta - 1}}{\Gamma(\vartheta)} e^{-\lambda(\psi(s) - \psi(t))} \psi'(s) g(s) ds. \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, the ψ -tempered fractional integral ${}_T^\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta; \psi}$ reduces to the ψ -Riemann-Liouville fractional integral [5, 6] if $\lambda = 0$.

By incorporating Definition 2.2 and Definition 2.3, we can now present the subsequent definition of a broader fractional integral that encompasses both integrals as specific instances.

Definition 2.4 (The (k, ψ) -tempered fractional Integral). Let $g \in X_\psi^p(a, b)$ and $[a, b]$ be a finite or infinite interval on the real axis $\mathbb{R} = (-\infty, \infty)$, $\psi(t) > 0$ be an increasing function on (a, b) and $\psi'(t) > 0$ be continuous on (a, b) , $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, $k > 0$ and $\vartheta > 0$. The (k, ψ) -tempered fractional integral operators of a function g (left-sided and right-sided) of order ϑ and index λ are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} {}_T^\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} g(t) &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} (g(t)e^{\lambda\psi(t)}) = \int_a^t \bar{\Psi}_\vartheta^{k, \psi}(t, s) e^{-\lambda(\psi(t) - \psi(s))} \psi'(s) g(s) ds, \\ {}_T^\lambda \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} g(t) &= e^{\lambda\psi(t)} \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} (g(t)e^{-\lambda\psi(t)}) = \int_t^b \bar{\Psi}_\vartheta^{k, \psi}(s, t) e^{-\lambda(\psi(s) - \psi(t))} \psi'(s) g(s) ds, \end{aligned}$$

with $\bar{\Psi}_\vartheta^{k, \psi}(t, s) = \frac{(\psi(t) - \psi(s))^{\frac{\vartheta}{k} - 1}}{k\Gamma_k(\vartheta)}$. Now, the (k, ψ) -tempered fractional integral ${}_T^\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi}$ reduces to the ψ -tempered fractional integral ${}_T^\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta; \psi}$ if $k = 1$.

2.2. Fractional derivatives

In this section, we present the definitions of various fractional derivatives that are utilized.

Definition 2.5 (*k*-Generalized ψ -Hilfer Derivative [5, 6]). Let $n - 1 < \frac{\vartheta}{k} \leq n$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $J = [a, b]$ an interval such that $-\infty \leq a < b \leq \infty$ and $g, \psi \in C^n([a, b], \mathbb{R})$ two functions such that ψ is increasing and $\psi'(t) \neq 0$, for all $t \in J$. The *k*-generalized ψ -Hilfer fractional derivatives (left-sided and right-sided) ${}^H_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r; \psi}(\cdot)$ and ${}^H_k \mathcal{D}_{b-}^{\vartheta, r; \psi}(\cdot)$ of a function g of order ϑ and type $0 \leq r \leq 1$, with $k > 0$ are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} {}^H_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r; \psi} g(t) &= \left(\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{r(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(t)} \frac{d}{dt} \right)^n \left(k^n \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \\ &= \left(\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{r(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} \delta_{\psi}^n \left(k^n \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} {}^H_k \mathcal{D}_{b-}^{\vartheta, r; \psi} g(t) &= \left(\mathcal{J}_{b-}^{r(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'(t)} \frac{d}{dt} \right)^n \left(k^n \mathcal{J}_{b-}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \\ &= \left(\mathcal{J}_{b-}^{r(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} (-1)^n \delta_{\psi}^n \left(k^n \mathcal{J}_{b-}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} g \right) \right) (t), \end{aligned}$$

where $\delta_{\psi}^n = \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(t)} \frac{d}{dt} \right)^n$.

Definition 2.6 (The tempered ψ -Hilfer Derivative [19]). Let $n - 1 < \vartheta \leq n$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, $J = [a, b]$ an interval such that $-\infty \leq a < b \leq \infty$ and $g, \psi \in C^n([a, b], \mathbb{R})$ two functions such that ψ is increasing and $\psi'(t) \neq 0$, for all $t \in J$. The tempered ψ -Hilfer fractional derivatives (left-sided and right-sided) ${}^{TH} \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi}(\cdot)$ and ${}^{TH} \mathcal{D}_{b-}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi}(\cdot)$ of a function g of order ϑ , index λ and type $0 \leq r \leq 1$, are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{TH} \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi} g(t) &= \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{r(n-\vartheta); \psi} \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(t)} \frac{d}{dt} + \lambda \right)^n \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(1-r)(n-\vartheta); \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \\ &= \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{r(n-\vartheta); \psi} \mathfrak{U}_{\psi}^n \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(1-r)(n-\vartheta); \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \\ &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \times {}^H \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r; \psi} \left(g(t) e^{\lambda\psi(t)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{TH} \mathcal{D}_{b-}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi} g(t) &= \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{b-}^{r(n-\vartheta); \psi} \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'(t)} \frac{d}{dt} + \lambda \right)^n \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{b-}^{(1-r)(n-\vartheta); \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \\ &= \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{b-}^{r(n-\vartheta); \psi} (-1)^n \mathfrak{U}_{\psi}^n \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{b-}^{(1-r)(n-\vartheta); \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \\ &= e^{\lambda\psi(t)} \times {}^H \mathcal{D}_{b-}^{\vartheta, r; \psi} \left(g(t) e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathfrak{U}_{\psi}^n = \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(t)} \frac{d}{dt} + \lambda \right)^n$, ${}^H \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r; \psi}(\cdot)$ and ${}^H \mathcal{D}_{b-}^{\vartheta, r; \psi}(\cdot)$ are the left-sided and right-sided ψ -Hilfer fractional derivatives, defined in [41].

By incorporating Definition 2.5 and Definition 2.6, we will now give the following definition of a more generalized fractional derivative that encompasses both tempered ψ -Hilfer derivative and *k*-generalized ψ -Hilfer derivative as specific cases.

Definition 2.7 (The tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer Derivative). Let $n - 1 < \frac{\vartheta}{k} \leq n$ with $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, $k > 0$, $J = [a, b]$ an interval such that $-\infty \leq a < b \leq \infty$ and $g, \psi \in C^n([a, b], \mathbb{R})$ two functions such that ψ is increasing and $\psi'(t) \neq 0$, for all $t \in J$. The tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer fractional derivatives (left-sided and right-sided) ${}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi}(\cdot)$ and ${}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{b-}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi}(\cdot)$ of a function g of order ϑ , index λ and type $0 \leq r \leq 1$, are defined by

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi} g(t) &= \left({}^T\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{r(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(t)} \frac{d}{dt} + \lambda \right)^n \left(k^n {}^T\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \\ &= \left({}^T\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{r(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} \mathfrak{U}_{\psi}^n \left(k^n {}^T\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \\ &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \times {}^H\mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r; \psi} \left(g(t)e^{\lambda\psi(t)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} {}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{b-}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi} g(t) &= \left({}^T\mathcal{J}_{b-}^{r(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} \left(-\frac{1}{\psi'(t)} \frac{d}{dt} + \lambda \right)^n \left(k^n {}^T\mathcal{J}_{b-}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \\ &= \left({}^T\mathcal{J}_{b-}^{r(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} (-1)^n \mathfrak{U}_{\psi}^n \left(k^n {}^T\mathcal{J}_{b-}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta), k; \psi} g \right) \right) (t) \\ &= e^{\lambda\psi(t)} \times {}^H\mathcal{D}_{b-}^{\vartheta, r; \psi} \left(g(t)e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \right), \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathfrak{U}_{\psi}^n = \left(\frac{1}{\psi'(t)} \frac{d}{dt} + \lambda \right)^n$. The tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer fractional derivative ${}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi}$ reduces to the tempered ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative ${}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi}$ if $k = 1$.

Remark 2.8. It is worth noting that the tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer fractional derivative is thought to be an expansion to many fractional operators defined over the years; indeed, in the following part, we will give a list of some of the most commonly used fractional derivatives that are considered to be a particular case of our operator by modifying the parameters λ, k, ϑ, r , and the function ψ . The fractional derivative ${}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta, r, \lambda; \psi}$ interpolate the following fractional derivatives:

- The tempered ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative ($k = 1$) [19];
- The tempered (k, ψ) -Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative ($r = 0$);
- The tempered ψ -Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative ($r = 0, k = 1$) [22];
- The tempered (k, ψ) -Caputo fractional derivative ($r = 1$) [22];
- The tempered ψ -Caputo fractional derivative ($r = 1, k = 1$) [22];
- The tempered k -Hilfer fractional derivative ($\psi(t) = t$) [5, 6];
- The ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative ($k = 1, \lambda = 0$) [41];
- The ψ -Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative ($k = 1, r = 0, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];
- The ψ -Caputo fractional derivative ($k = 1, r = 1, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];
- The Hilfer fractional derivative ($k = 1, \psi(t) = t, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];
- The Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative ($k = 1, \psi(t) = t, r = 0, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];
- The Caputo fractional derivative ($k = 1, \psi(t) = t, r = 1, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];
- The Hilfer–Hadamard fractional derivative ($k = 1, \psi(t) = \ln(t), \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];

- The Caputo–Hadamard fractional derivative ($k = 1, \psi(t) = \ln(t), r = 1, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];
- The Hadamard fractional derivative ($k = 1, \psi(t) = \ln(t), r = 0, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];
- The Hilfer–generalized fractional derivative ($k = 1, \psi(t) = t^\rho, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];
- The Caputo–generalized fractional derivative ($k = 1, \psi(t) = t^\rho, r = 1, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];
- The generalized fractional derivative ($k = 1, \psi(t) = t^\rho, r = 0, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6];
- The Weyl fractional derivative ($k = 1, \psi(t) = t^\rho, r = 0, a = -\infty, \lambda = 0$) [5, 6].

2.3. *Necessary properties of fractional operators*

Subsequently, employing Definition 2.4, particularly highlighting the notion that we have the ability to write

$${}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} g(t) = e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \left(g(t) e^{\lambda\psi(t)} \right),$$

and by following the same steps of Theorem 2.2 and Theorem 2.3 from [36], we can deduce the following theorems.

Theorem 2.9. *Let $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an integrable function, and take $\vartheta > 0, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ and $k > 0$. Then ${}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} g$ exists for all $t \in [a, b]$.*

Theorem 2.10. *Let $g \in X^p_\psi(a, b)$ and take $\vartheta > 0, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ and $k > 0$. Then ${}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} g \in C([a, b], \mathbb{R})$.*

Lemma 2.11. *Let $\vartheta > 0, r > 0, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ and $k > 0$. Then, we have the following semigroup property given by*

$${}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{r, k; \psi} f(t) = {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta+r, k; \psi} f(t) = {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{r, k; \psi} {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} f(t)$$

and

$${}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{r, k; \psi} f(t) = {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{\vartheta+r, k; \psi} f(t) = {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{r, k; \psi} {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} f(t).$$

Proof. By Definition 2.4 and Lemma 2.4 in [36], for $\vartheta > 0, r > 0, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ and $k > 0$, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{r, k; \psi} f(t) &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \left(e^{\lambda\psi(t)} {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{r, k; \psi} f(t) \right) \\ &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{r, k; \psi} \left(e^{\lambda\psi(t)} f(t) \right) \\ &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta+r, k; \psi} \left(e^{\lambda\psi(t)} f(t) \right) \\ &= {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta+r, k; \psi} f(t). \end{aligned}$$

We have also,

$$\begin{aligned} {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{r, k; \psi} f(t) &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{r, k; \psi} \left(e^{\lambda\psi(t)} f(t) \right) \\ &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{r, k; \psi} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \left(e^{\lambda\psi(t)} f(t) \right) \\ &= {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{r, k; \psi} {}^T_\lambda \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} f(t). \end{aligned}$$

The case of right-sided fractional operator follows from the same steps. □

Lemma 2.12 ([36]). *Let $\vartheta, r > 0$, and $k > 0$. Then, we have*

$$\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \bar{\Psi}_r^{k, \psi}(t, a) = \bar{\Psi}_{\vartheta+r}^{k, \psi}(t, a)$$

and

$$\mathcal{J}_{b^-}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \bar{\Psi}_r^{k, \psi}(b, t) = \bar{\Psi}_{\vartheta+r}^{k, \psi}(b, t).$$

Lemma 2.13. *Let $\vartheta, r > 0, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ and $k > 0$. Then, we have*

$${}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} \bar{\Psi}_r^{k, \psi}(t, a) = e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} \bar{\Psi}_{\vartheta+r}^{k, \psi}(t, a)$$

and

$${}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{b-}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} e^{\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} \bar{\Psi}_r^{k, \psi}(b, t) = e^{\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} \bar{\Psi}_{\vartheta+r}^{k, \psi}(b, t).$$

Proof. From Definition 2.4, we have

$${}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} \bar{\Psi}_r^{k, \psi}(t, a) = e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \bar{\Psi}_r^{k, \psi}(t, a).$$

We know by Lemma 2.12, that

$$\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \bar{\Psi}_r^{k, \psi}(t, a) = \bar{\Psi}_{\vartheta+r}^{k, \psi}(t, a).$$

Thus,

$${}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} \bar{\Psi}_r^{k, \psi}(t, a) = e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} \bar{\Psi}_{\vartheta+r}^{k, \psi}(t, a).$$

The case of right-sided fractional operator follows from the same steps. □

Theorem 2.14. *Let $0 < a < b < \infty, \vartheta > 0, 0 \leq \xi < 1, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}, k > 0$ and $x \in C_{\xi; \psi}(J)$. If $\frac{\vartheta}{k} > 1 - \xi$, then*

$$\left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} x \right) (a) = \lim_{t \rightarrow a^+} \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} x \right) (t) = 0.$$

Proof. $x \in C_{\xi; \psi}(J)$ means that $\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a)x(t) \in C(J, \mathbb{R})$, then there exists a positive constant R such that for $t \in (a, b]$ we have

$$|\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a)x(t)| < R,$$

thus,

$$|x(t)| < R\Gamma_k(k\xi) |\bar{\Psi}_{k\xi}^{k, \psi}(t, a)|. \tag{2.1}$$

Now, we apply the operator ${}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi}(\cdot)$ on both sides of Equation (2.1), so that we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} x \right) (t) \right| &< R\Gamma_k(k\xi) \left| \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \bar{\Psi}_{k\xi}^{k, \psi}(s, a) \right) (t) \right| \\ &< R\Gamma_k(k\xi) \left| \left(\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(s))} \bar{\Psi}_{k\xi}^{k, \psi}(s, a) \right) (t) \right|. \end{aligned}$$

We know by Lemma 2.12, that

$$\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \bar{\Psi}_r^{k, \psi}(t, a) = \bar{\Psi}_{\vartheta+r}^{k, \psi}(t, a).$$

Also, we have

$$\widehat{\lambda} := \max_{(t,s) \in J \times [a,t]} e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(s))} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \lambda \geq 0, \\ e^{-\lambda(\psi(b)-\psi(a))}, & \text{if } \lambda < 0. \end{cases}$$

Consequently, we may write

$$\left| \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} x \right) (t) \right| < R\widehat{\lambda}\Gamma_k(k\xi) \bar{\Psi}_{\vartheta+k\xi}^{k, \psi}(t, a).$$

Then, we have the right-hand side $\rightarrow 0$ as $x \rightarrow a$, and

$$\left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} x \right) (a) = \lim_{t \rightarrow a^+} \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} x \right) (t) = 0.$$

□

Lemma 2.15. *Let $t > a$, $\vartheta > 0$, $0 \leq r \leq 1$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, $k > 0$. Then for $0 < \xi < 1$; $\xi = \frac{1}{k}(r(k - \vartheta) + \vartheta)$, we have*

$$\left[{}^{TH}_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} \left(\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(s, a) \right)^{-1} e^{-\lambda(\psi(s)-\psi(a))} \right] (t) = 0.$$

Proof. From Definitions 2.7 and Lemma 2.8 from [36], we have

$$\left[{}^{TH}_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} \left(\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(s, a) \right)^{-1} e^{-\lambda(\psi(s)-\psi(a))} \right] (t) = \left[e^{-\lambda(\psi(s)-\psi(a))} {}^H_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r;\psi} \left(\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(s, a) \right)^{-1} \right] (t),$$

and

$$\left[{}^H_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r;\psi} \left(\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(s, a) \right)^{-1} \right] (t) = 0.$$

Thus,

$$\left[{}^{TH}_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} \left(\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(s, a) \right)^{-1} e^{-\lambda(\psi(s)-\psi(a))} \right] (t) = 0.$$

□

Theorem 2.16. *If $f \in C_{\xi;\psi}^n[a, b]$, $n - 1 < \frac{\vartheta}{k} < n$, $0 \leq r \leq 1$, $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, where $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $k > 0$, then*

$$\begin{aligned} & \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} {}^{TH}_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} f \right) (t) \\ &= f(t) - e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\psi(t) - \psi(a))^{\xi-i}}{k^{i-n} \Gamma_k(k(\xi - i + 1))} \left\{ \delta_{\psi}^{n-i} \left(\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta),k;\psi} f(a) e^{\lambda\psi(a)} \right) \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\xi = \frac{1}{k} (r(kn - \vartheta) + \vartheta).$$

In particular, if $n = 1$, we have

$$\left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} {}^{TH}_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} f \right) (t) = f(t) - e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} \frac{(\psi(t) - \psi(a))^{\xi-1}}{\Gamma_k(r(k - \vartheta) + \vartheta)} {}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi} f(a).$$

Proof. From Definition 2.4 and Definition 2.7, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} {}^{TH}_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} f \right) (t) &= {}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} \left(e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \times {}^H_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r;\psi} \left(f(t) e^{\lambda\psi(t)} \right) \right) \\ &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} {}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} \left({}^H_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r;\psi} \left(f(t) e^{\lambda\psi(t)} \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we know from [36], that

$$\left(\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} {}^H_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r;\psi} f \right) (t) = f(t) - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\psi(t) - \psi(a))^{\xi-i}}{k^{i-n} \Gamma_k(k(\xi - i + 1))} \left\{ \delta_{\psi}^{n-i} \left(\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta),k;\psi} f(a) \right) \right\}.$$

As a consequence, we may write

$$\begin{aligned} & \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} {}^{TH}_k \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} f \right) (t) \\ &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \left[f(t) e^{\lambda\psi(t)} - \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\psi(t) - \psi(a))^{\xi-i}}{k^{i-n} \Gamma_k(k(\xi - i + 1))} \left\{ \delta_{\psi}^{n-i} \left(\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta),k;\psi} f(a) e^{\lambda\psi(a)} \right) \right\} \right] \\ &= f(t) - e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(\psi(t) - \psi(a))^{\xi-i}}{k^{i-n} \Gamma_k(k(\xi - i + 1))} \left\{ \delta_{\psi}^{n-i} \left(\mathcal{J}_{a+}^{(1-r)(kn-\vartheta),k;\psi} f(a) e^{\lambda\psi(a)} \right) \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

□

Lemma 2.17. *Let $\vartheta > 0, 0 \leq r \leq 1, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, and $x \in C^1_{\xi;\psi}(J)$, where $k > 0$, then for $t \in (a, b]$, we have*

$$\left({}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} \frac{T}{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} x \right) (t) = x(t).$$

Proof. We have from Definition 2.4 and Definition 2.7 that

$$\begin{aligned} \left({}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} \frac{T}{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} x \right) (t) &= {}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} \left(e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} \left(x(t)e^{\lambda\psi(t)} \right) \right) \\ &= e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} \left({}^{\text{H}}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r;\psi} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} \left(x(t)e^{\lambda\psi(t)} \right) \right). \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we know by Lemma 2.10 from [36], that we have

$$\left({}^{\text{H}}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r;\psi} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} x \right) (t) = x(t).$$

Thus,

$$\left({}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} \frac{T}{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} x \right) (t) = e^{-\lambda\psi(t)} x(t) e^{\lambda\psi(t)} = x(t).$$

□

3. Existence of Solutions

We consider the following fractional differential equation

$$\left({}^{\text{TH}}\mathcal{D}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi} x \right) (t) = \varphi(t), \quad t \in (a, b], \tag{3.1}$$

where $0 < \vartheta < k, 0 \leq r \leq 1, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ with the condition

$$\left(\frac{T}{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi} x \right) (a^+) = x_0, \tag{3.2}$$

where $\xi = \frac{r(k-\vartheta)+\vartheta}{k}, k > 0, \varphi(\cdot) \in C(J, \mathbb{R}), x_0 \in \mathbb{R}$.

The following theorem shows that the problem (3.1)-(3.2) have a unique solution.

Theorem 3.1. *Let $0 < \vartheta < k, 0 \leq r \leq 1, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}, k > 0, \varphi(\cdot) \in C(J, \mathbb{R})$. The problem (3.1)-(3.2) has a unique solution given by:*

$$x(t) = \frac{x_0 e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))}}{\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a) \Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \left(\frac{T}{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} \varphi \right) (t). \tag{3.3}$$

Proof. Assume x satisfies (3.1)-(3.2). By applying the fractional integral operator $\frac{T}{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi}(\cdot)$ on both sides of the fractional equation (3.1) and using Theorem 2.16, we obtain

$$x(t) = \frac{\frac{T}{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi} x(a)}{\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a) \Gamma_k(k\xi)} e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} + \left(\frac{T}{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} \varphi \right) (t).$$

Using the condition (3.2), we get

$$x(t) = \frac{x_0 e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))}}{\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a) \Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \left(\frac{T}{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} \varphi \right) (t).$$

Reciprocally, applying ${}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi}$ on both sides of (3.3) and using Lemma 2.13 and Lemma 2.11, we get

$$\left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi} x\right)(t) = x_0 e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))} + \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{k(1-\xi)+\vartheta,k;\psi} \varphi\right)(t), \quad t \in (a, b]. \tag{3.4}$$

Next, taking the limit $t \rightarrow a^+$ of (3.4) and using Theorem 2.14, with $k(1-\xi) < k(1-\xi) + \vartheta$, we obtain

$$\left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{k(1-\xi),k;\psi} x\right)(a^+) = x_0, \tag{3.5}$$

which shows that the initial condition (3.2) is satisfied. Next, apply operator ${}^T_k H \mathcal{D}_{a+}^{\vartheta,r,\lambda;\psi}(\cdot)$ on both sides of (3.3). Then, from Lemma 2.15 and Lemma 2.17 we obtain equation (3.1). This completes the proof. \square

As a consequence of Theorem 3.1, we have the following result.

Lemma 3.2. *Let $\xi = \frac{r(k-\vartheta) + \vartheta}{k}$ where $0 < \vartheta < k$ and $0 \leq r \leq 1, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}$, let $f : J \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a continuous function. Then, the problem (1.1)-(1.2) is equivalent to the following integral equation:*

$$x(t) = \frac{x_0 e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))}}{\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a) \Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} \varphi\right)(t), \tag{3.6}$$

where φ be a function satisfying the functional equation

$$\varphi(t) = f(t, x(t), \varphi(t)).$$

The following hypotheses will be used in the sequel :

- (Ax1) The function $f : J \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous.
- (Ax2) There exist constants $\zeta_1 > 0$ and $0 < \zeta_2 < 1$ such that

$$|f(t, x_1, y_1) - f(t, x_2, y_2)| \leq \zeta_1 |x_1 - x_2| + \zeta_2 |y_1 - y_2|$$

for any $x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ and $t \in J$.

Set

$$\widehat{\lambda} := \max_{(t,s) \in J \times [a,t]} e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(s))} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } \lambda \geq 0, \\ e^{-\lambda(\psi(b)-\psi(a))}, & \text{if } \lambda < 0. \end{cases}$$

We are now in a position to state and prove our existence result for the problem (1.1)-(1.2) based on based on Banach’s fixed point theorem [13].

Theorem 3.3. *Assume (Ax1)-(Ax2) hold. If*

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{\zeta_1 \widehat{\lambda} \Gamma_k(k\xi) (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{\frac{\vartheta}{k}}}{\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k\xi)(1 - \zeta_2)} < 1, \tag{3.7}$$

then the problem (1.1)-(1.2) has a unique solution in $C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$.

Proof. Transform problem (1.1)-(1.2) into a fixed point problem by considering the operator $\mathcal{T} : C_{\xi;\psi}(J) \rightarrow C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$ by

$$(\mathcal{T}x)(t) = \frac{x_0 e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))}}{\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a) \Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a+}^{\vartheta,k;\psi} \varphi\right)(t), \tag{3.8}$$

where φ be a function satisfying the functional equation

$$\varphi(t) = f(t, x(t), \varphi(t)).$$

By Theorem 2.10, we have $\mathcal{T}x \in C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$. We show that the operator \mathcal{T} has a unique fixed point in $C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$.

Let $x, y \in C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$. Then for any for $t \in J$, we have

$$|\mathcal{T}x(t) - \mathcal{T}y(t)| \leq \left({}^T \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} |\varphi_1(s) - \varphi_2(s)| \right) (t),$$

where φ_1 and φ_2 be functions satisfying the functional equations

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_1(t) &= f(t, x(t), \varphi_1(t)), \\ \varphi_2(t) &= f(t, y(t), \varphi_2(t)). \end{aligned}$$

By (Ax2), we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\varphi_1(t) - \varphi_2(t)| &= |f(t, x(t), \varphi_1(t)) - f(t, y(t), \varphi_2(t))| \\ &\leq \zeta_1 |x(t) - y(t)| + \zeta_2 |\varphi_1(t) - \varphi_2(t)|. \end{aligned}$$

Then,

$$|\varphi_1(t) - \varphi_2(t)| \leq \frac{\zeta_1}{1 - \zeta_2} |x(t) - y(t)|.$$

Therefore, for each $t \in J$ we get

$$|\mathcal{T}x(t) - \mathcal{T}y(t)| \leq \frac{\zeta_1}{1 - \zeta_2} \left({}^T \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} |x(s) - y(s)| \right) (t).$$

Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{T}x(t) - \mathcal{T}y(t)| &\leq \frac{\zeta_1}{1 - \zeta_2} \|x - y\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} \left({}^T \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} (\psi(s) - \psi(a))^{\xi-1} \right) (t) \\ &\leq \frac{\zeta_1}{1 - \zeta_2} \|x - y\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} \left(\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} e^{-\lambda(\psi(t) - \psi(s))} (\psi(s) - \psi(a))^{\xi-1} \right) (t). \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2.12, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{T}x(t) - \mathcal{T}y(t)| &\leq \frac{\zeta_1 \widehat{\lambda}}{1 - \zeta_2} \|x - y\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} \left(\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} (\psi(s) - \psi(a))^{\xi-1} \right) (t) \\ &\leq \frac{\zeta_1 \widehat{\lambda} \Gamma_k(k\xi)}{\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k\xi)(1 - \zeta_2)} \|x - y\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} (\psi(t) - \psi(a))^{\frac{\vartheta + k\xi}{k} - 1}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a) (\mathcal{T}x(t) - \mathcal{T}y(t)) \right| &\leq \frac{\zeta_1 \widehat{\lambda} \Gamma_k(k\xi)}{\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k\xi)(1 - \zeta_2)} \|x - y\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} (\psi(t) - \psi(a))^{\frac{\vartheta}{k}} \\ &\leq \frac{\zeta_1 \widehat{\lambda} \Gamma_k(k\xi) (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{\frac{\vartheta}{k}}}{\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k\xi)(1 - \zeta_2)} \|x - y\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}}. \end{aligned}$$

Thus,

$$\|\mathcal{T}x - \mathcal{T}y\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} \leq \mathcal{L} \|x - y\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}}.$$

By (3.7), the operator \mathcal{T} is a contraction on $C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$. Hence, by Banach’s contraction principle, \mathcal{T} has a unique fixed point $x \in C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$, which is a solution to our problem (1.1)-(1.2). \square

4. Existence Results for the Nonlocal Problem

This section is devoted to the study of existence result for the problem (1.3)-(1.4) which is based on Schaefer’s fixed point theorem [13].

Definition 4.1. By a solution of problem (1.3)-(1.4) we mean a function $x \in C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$ that satisfies the equation (1.3) and the nonlocal condition (1.4).

Lemma 4.2. Let $\xi = \frac{r(k - \vartheta) + \vartheta}{k}$ where $0 < \vartheta < k$ and $0 \leq r \leq 1, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}, f : J \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\Phi : C_{\xi;\psi}(J) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are continuous functions. Then, the problem (1.3)-(1.4) is equivalent to the following integral equation:

$$x(t) = \frac{(x_0 - \Phi(x))e^{-\lambda(\psi(t) - \psi(a))}}{\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a)\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \left({}^T \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \varphi \right) (t), \tag{4.1}$$

where φ be a function satisfying the functional equation

$$\varphi(t) = f(t, x(t), \varphi(t)).$$

Let us introduce the following hypotheses:

(Ax3) There exist functions $\widehat{\zeta}_1 \in C(J, \mathbb{R}_+)$ and $\widehat{\zeta}_2 \in C(J, [0, 1))$ such that

$$|f(t, x_1, y_1) - f(t, x_2, y_2)| \leq \widehat{\zeta}_1(t)\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a)|x_1 - x_2| + \widehat{\zeta}_2(t)|y_1 - y_2|$$

for any $x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ and $t \in J$.

(Ax4) There exists a constant $\gamma > 0$ such that

$$|\Phi(x_1) - \Phi(x_2)| \leq \gamma \|x_1 - x_2\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}}$$

for any $x_1, x_2 \in C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$ and $t \in J$.

Remark 4.3. We note that by taking:

$$\widehat{\zeta}_1(t) = q_2(t), \widehat{\zeta}_2(t) = q_3(t), q_1(t) = |f(t, 0, 0)|,$$

hypothesis (Ax3) implies that

$$|f(t, x, y)| \leq q_1(t) + q_2(t)\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a)|x| + q_3(t)|y|,$$

for $t \in (a, b], x, y \in \mathbb{R}$, where $q_1, q_2, q_3 \in C(J, \mathbb{R}_+)$ with

$$q_1^* = \sup_{t \in J} q_1(t), q_2^* = \sup_{t \in J} q_2(t), q_3^* = \sup_{t \in J} q_3(t) < 1.$$

Theorem 4.4. Assume (Ax1), (Ax3) and (Ax4) hold. If

$$\tilde{\mathcal{X}} = \frac{\widehat{\lambda}\gamma}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{q_2^*\widehat{\lambda}}{(1 - q_3^*)\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{1 - \xi + \frac{\vartheta}{k}} < 1, \tag{4.2}$$

then the problem (1.3)-(1.4) has at least one solution in $C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$.

Proof. Transform problem (1.3)-(1.4) into a fixed point problem by considering the operator $\mathcal{Z} : C_{\xi;\psi}(J) \rightarrow C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$ by

$$(\mathcal{Z}x)(t) = \frac{(x_0 - \Phi(x))e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))}}{\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a)\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} \varphi \right) (t), \tag{4.3}$$

where φ be a function satisfying the functional equation

$$\varphi(t) = f(t, x(t), \varphi(t)).$$

In several steps, we will use Schaefer’s fixed point theorem to prove that the operator \mathcal{Z} has a fixed point.

Step 1: The operator \mathcal{Z} is continuous.

Let $\{x_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence such that $x_n \rightarrow x$ in $C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$. For $t \in J$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a)(\mathcal{Z}x_n(t) - \mathcal{Z}x(t))| &\leq \frac{e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))}}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} |\Phi(x_n) - \Phi(x)| \\ &\quad + \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} |\varphi_n(s) - \varphi(s)| \right) (t), \end{aligned}$$

where φ and φ_n be functions satisfying the functional equations

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi(t) &= f(t, x(t), \varphi(t)), \\ \varphi_n(t) &= f(t, x_n(t), \varphi_n(t)). \end{aligned}$$

Since $x_n \rightarrow x$, then we get $\varphi_n(t) \rightarrow \varphi(t)$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for each $t \in (a, b]$, and since f and Φ are continuous, then we have

$$\|\mathcal{Z}x_n - \mathcal{Z}x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Step 2: We prove that \mathcal{Z} is the mapping of two bounded sets in $C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$.

For M a positive constant, there exists a positive constant \mathcal{R} such that for

$$B_M = \{x \in C_{\xi;\psi}(J) : \|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} \leq M\},$$

we have $\|\mathcal{Z}(x)\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} \leq \mathcal{R}$.

For each $t \in J$, (4.3) implies that

$$|\mathcal{Z}x(t)| \leq \frac{(|x_0| + |\Phi(x)|)e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))}}{\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a)\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \left({}^T_{\lambda} \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} |\varphi(s)| \right) (t). \tag{4.4}$$

By the hypothesis (Ax3) and Remark 4.3, for $t \in J$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\varphi(t)| &= |f(t, x(t), \varphi(t))| \\ &\leq q_1(t) + q_2(t)\Psi_{\xi}^{\psi}(t, a)|x(t)| + q_3(t)|\varphi(t)|, \end{aligned}$$

which implies that

$$|\varphi(t)| \leq q_1^* + q_2^*M + q_3^*|\varphi(t)|,$$

then

$$|\varphi(t)| \leq \frac{q_1^* + q_2^*M}{1 - q_3^*} := \Delta.$$

Thus for $t \in J$, by hypotheses $(Ax3)$, $(Ax4)$, Remark 4.3 and from (4.4) we get

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a)\mathcal{Z}x(t)| &\leq \frac{(|x_0| + \gamma M + |\Phi(0)|)e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))}}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \Delta\Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a) \left({}^T\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi}(1) \right) (t) \\ &\leq \frac{(|x_0| + \gamma M + |\Phi(0)|)e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))}}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} \\ &\quad + \Delta\Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a) \left(\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(s))} \right) (t) \\ &\leq \frac{\widehat{\lambda}(|x_0| + \gamma M + |\Phi(0)|)}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \Delta\widehat{\lambda}\Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a) \left(\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi}(1) \right) (t). \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2.13, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a)\mathcal{Z}x(t)| &\leq \frac{\widehat{\lambda}(|x_0| + \gamma M + |\Phi(0)|)}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{\Delta\widehat{\lambda}}{\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(t) - \psi(a))^{1-\xi+\frac{\vartheta}{k}} \\ &\leq \frac{\widehat{\lambda}(|x_0| + \gamma M + |\Phi(0)|)}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{\Delta\widehat{\lambda}}{\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{1-\xi+\frac{\vartheta}{k}}. \end{aligned}$$

Then, for each $t \in J$ we obtain

$$\|\mathcal{Z}x\|_{C_{\xi; \psi}} \leq \frac{\widehat{\lambda}(|x_0| + \gamma M + |\Phi(0)|)}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{\Delta\widehat{\lambda}}{\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{1-\xi+\frac{\vartheta}{k}} := \mathcal{R}.$$

Step 3: \mathcal{Z} maps bounded sets into equicontinuous sets of $C_{\xi; \psi}(J)$.

Let $\tau_1, \tau_2 \in J$, $\tau_1 < \tau_2$ and let $x \in B_M$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_1, a)\mathcal{Z}x(\tau_1) - \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_2, a)\mathcal{Z}x(\tau_2) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{(|x_0| + |\Phi(x)|) \left| e^{-\lambda(\psi(\tau_1)-\psi(a))} - e^{-\lambda(\psi(\tau_2)-\psi(a))} \right|}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} \\ &\quad + \left| \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_1, a) \left({}^T\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} |\varphi(s)| \right) (\tau_1) - \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_2, a) \left({}^T\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} |\varphi(s)| \right) (\tau_2) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{(|x_0| + |\Phi(x)|) \left| e^{-\lambda(\psi(\tau_1)-\psi(a))} - e^{-\lambda(\psi(\tau_2)-\psi(a))} \right|}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} \\ &\quad + \int_a^{\tau_1} \left| \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_1, a) \bar{\Psi}_\vartheta^{k, \psi}(\tau_1, s) e^{-\lambda(\psi(\tau_1)-\psi(s))} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_2, a) \bar{\Psi}_\vartheta^{k, \psi}(\tau_2, s) e^{-\lambda(\psi(\tau_2)-\psi(s))} \right| |\psi'(s)\varphi(s)| ds \\ &\quad + \left| \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_2, a) \left({}^T\mathcal{J}_{\tau_1^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi} |\varphi(s)| \right) (\tau_2) \right| \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2.13, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_1, a)\mathcal{Z}x(\tau_1) - \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_2, a)\mathcal{Z}x(\tau_2) \right| &\leq \frac{(|x_0| + |\Phi(x)|) \left| e^{-\lambda(\psi(\tau_1)-\psi(a))} - e^{-\lambda(\psi(\tau_2)-\psi(a))} \right|}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} \\ &\quad + \Delta \int_a^{\tau_1} \left| \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_1, a) \bar{\Psi}_\vartheta^{k, \psi}(\tau_1, s) e^{-\lambda(\psi(\tau_1)-\psi(s))} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_2, a) \bar{\Psi}_\vartheta^{k, \psi}(\tau_2, s) e^{-\lambda(\psi(\tau_2)-\psi(s))} \right| |\psi'(s)| ds \\ &\quad + \frac{\Delta\widehat{\lambda}\Psi_\xi^\psi(\tau_2, a) (\psi(\tau_2) - \psi(\tau_1))^{\frac{\vartheta}{k}}}{\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)}. \end{aligned}$$

As $\tau_1 \rightarrow \tau_2$, the right-hand side of the above inequality tends to zero. From Step 1 to Step 3 with Arzela-Ascoli theorem, we conclude that $\mathcal{Z} : C_{\xi;\psi}(J) \rightarrow C_{\xi;\psi}(J)$ continuous and completely continuous.

Step 4: A priori bound. Now it remains to show that the set

$$\mathcal{G} = \{x \in C_{\xi;\psi}(J) : x = \eta\mathcal{Z}(x) \text{ for some } 0 < \eta < 1\}$$

is bounded. Let $x \in \mathcal{G}$, then $x = \eta\mathcal{Z}(x)$ for some $0 < \eta < 1$.

By the hypothesis (Ax3) and Remark 4.3, for $t \in (a, b]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\varphi(t)| &= |f(t, x(t), \varphi(t))| \\ &\leq q_1(t) + q_2(t)\Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a)|x(t)| + q_3(t)|\varphi(t)|, \end{aligned}$$

which implies that

$$|\varphi(t)| \leq q_1^* + q_2^*\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} + q_3^*|\varphi(t)|,$$

then

$$|\varphi(t)| \leq \frac{q_1^* + q_2^*\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}}}{1 - q_3^*}.$$

Thus, for $t \in J$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a)x(t)| &\leq \frac{(|x_0| + \gamma\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} + |\Phi(0)|)e^{-\lambda(\psi(t)-\psi(a))}}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} \\ &\quad + \frac{q_1^* + q_2^*\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}}}{1 - q_3^*} \Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a) \left({}^T \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi}(1) \right) (t) \\ &\leq \frac{\widehat{\lambda}(|x_0| + \gamma\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} + |\Phi(0)|)}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} \\ &\quad + \frac{q_1^* + q_2^*\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}}}{1 - q_3^*} \widehat{\lambda} \Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a) \left(\mathcal{J}_{a^+}^{\vartheta, k; \psi}(1) \right) (t). \end{aligned}$$

By Lemma 2.13, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\Psi_\xi^\psi(t, a)x(t)| &\leq \frac{\widehat{\lambda}(|x_0| + \gamma\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} + |\Phi(0)|)}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{(q_1^* + q_2^*\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}})\widehat{\lambda}}{(1 - q_3^*)\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(t) - \psi(a))^{1-\xi+\frac{\vartheta}{k}} \\ &\leq \frac{\widehat{\lambda}(|x_0| + \gamma\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} + |\Phi(0)|)}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{(q_1^* + q_2^*\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}})\widehat{\lambda}}{(1 - q_3^*)\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{1-\xi+\frac{\vartheta}{k}} \\ &\leq \frac{\widehat{\lambda}(|x_0| + |\Phi(0)|)}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{q_1^*\widehat{\lambda}}{(1 - q_3^*)\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{1-\xi+\frac{\vartheta}{k}} \\ &\quad + \|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} \left[\frac{\widehat{\lambda}\gamma}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{q_2^*\widehat{\lambda}}{(1 - q_3^*)\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{1-\xi+\frac{\vartheta}{k}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Then, for each $t \in J$ we obtain

$$\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} \leq \mathcal{X} + \tilde{\mathcal{X}}\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}},$$

where

$$\mathcal{X} = \frac{\widehat{\lambda}(|x_0| + |\Phi(0)|)}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{q_1^*\widehat{\lambda}}{(1 - q_3^*)\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{1-\xi+\frac{\vartheta}{k}}$$

and

$$\tilde{\mathcal{X}} = \frac{\widehat{\lambda}\gamma}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{q_2^*\widehat{\lambda}}{(1 - q_3^*)\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{1-\xi+\frac{\vartheta}{k}}.$$

Thus, by (4.2) we have

$$\|x\|_{C_{\xi;\psi}} \leq \frac{\mathcal{X}}{1 - \tilde{\mathcal{X}}}.$$

As a consequence of Schaefer’s point theorem, we deduce that \mathcal{Z} has a fixed point which is a solution of the problem (1.3)-(1.4). □

5. Examples

In this section, we will present illustrative examples demonstrating the fulfillment of the requirements for the existence results theorems. To begin with, we will introduce the general case of our problem (1.1)-(1.2).

Example 5.1. By taking $r = \vartheta = \lambda = \frac{1}{2}$, $k = \frac{3}{2}$, $\psi(t) = t^2$, $a = 1$, $b = 2$ and $x_0 = 2$, from the problem (1.1)-(1.2), we obtain the following initial value problem with (k, ψ) -Hilfer nonlinear implicit fractional differential equation:

$$\left({}^{TH}\mathcal{D}_{1+}^{\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \psi} x \right) (t) = f \left(t, x(t), \left({}^{TH}\mathcal{D}_{1+}^{\frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}, \frac{1}{2}; \psi} x \right) (t) \right), \quad t \in (1, 2], \tag{5.1}$$

$$\left({}^T\mathcal{J}_{1+}^{\frac{2}{3}, \frac{2}{3}; \psi} x \right) (1^+) = 2, \tag{5.2}$$

where $J = [1, 2]$, $\xi = \frac{1}{k}(r(k - \vartheta) + \vartheta) = \frac{2}{3}$ and

$$f(t, x, y) = \frac{\sqrt[3]{t^2 - 1} |\sin(t)|(1 + x + y)}{136e^{-t+5}}, \quad t \in J, \quad x, y \in \mathbb{R}.$$

We have

$$C_{\xi;\psi}(J) = C_{\frac{2}{3};\psi}(J) = \left\{ x : (1, 2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : (\sqrt[3]{t^2 - 1})x \in C(J, \mathbb{R}) \right\}.$$

It is clear that the function f is continuous on J . Then, the condition (Ax1) is satisfied.

For each $x, \bar{x}, y, \bar{y} \in \mathbb{R}$ and $t \in J$, we have

$$|f(t, x, \bar{x}) - f(t, y, \bar{y})| \leq \frac{\sqrt[3]{t^2 - 1} |\sin(t)|}{136e^{-t+53}} (|x - \bar{x}| + |y - \bar{y}|), \quad t \in J,$$

and so the condition (Ax2) is satisfied with $\zeta_1 = \zeta_2 = \frac{\sqrt[3]{3}}{136e^3}$. Also, the condition (3.7) of Theorem 3.3 is satisfied. Indeed, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} &= \frac{\zeta_1 \widehat{\lambda} \Gamma_k(k\xi) (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{\frac{\vartheta}{k}}}{\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k\xi)(1 - \zeta_2)} \\ &= \frac{\sqrt[3]{9} \Gamma_{\frac{3}{2}}(1)}{\Gamma_{\frac{3}{2}}(\frac{3}{2})(136e^3 - \sqrt[3]{3})} \\ &= \frac{\sqrt[3]{6} \Gamma(\frac{1}{3})}{136e^3 - \sqrt[3]{3}} \\ &\approx 0.0017830088755347 \\ &< 1. \end{aligned}$$

Then the problem (5.1)-(5.2) has a unique solution in $C_{\frac{1}{2};\psi}([1, 2])$.

Example 5.2. Taking $r \rightarrow 0$, $\vartheta = \frac{1}{2}$, $\lambda = 0$, $k = 1$, $\psi(t) = \ln t$, $a = 1$, $b = e$ and $x_0 = \pi$, we get a particular case of problem (1.3)-(1.4) using the Hadamard fractional derivative, given by

$$\left({}^R_H \mathcal{D}_{1+}^{\frac{1}{2}, 0, 0; \psi} x \right) (t) = \left({}^H D_{1+}^{\frac{1}{2}} x \right) (t) = f \left(t, x(t), \left({}^H D_{1+}^{\frac{1}{2}} x \right) (t) \right), \quad t \in (1, e], \tag{5.3}$$

$$\left({}^T_0 \mathcal{J}_{1+}^{\frac{1}{2}, 1; \psi} x \right) (1^+) + \Phi(x) = \pi, \tag{5.4}$$

where $J = [1, e]$, $\xi = \frac{1}{k}(r(k - \vartheta) + \vartheta) = \frac{1}{2}$,

$$f(t, x, y) = \frac{11e + x\sqrt{\ln t} + y}{222e^t}, \quad t \in J, \quad x, y \in \mathbb{R},$$

and

$$\Phi(x) = \frac{27}{143} \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{\sqrt{\ln t}}{3^i} x(t), \quad t \in J, \quad x \in C_{\frac{1}{2}; \psi}(J).$$

We have

$$C_{\xi; \psi}(J) = C_{\frac{1}{2}; \psi}(J) = \left\{ x : (1, e] \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : (\sqrt{\ln t})x \in C(J, \mathbb{R}) \right\}.$$

Clearly, the continuous function f is continuous. Hence, the condition (Ax1) is satisfied.

For each $x, \bar{x}, y, \bar{y} \in \mathbb{R}$ and $t \in J$, we have

$$|f(t, x, \bar{x}) - f(t, y, \bar{y})| \leq \frac{\sqrt{\ln t}}{222e^t} |x - \bar{x}| + \frac{1}{222e^t} |y - \bar{y}|, \quad t \in J,$$

and so the condition (Ax3) is satisfied with $\hat{\zeta}_1(t) = \hat{\zeta}_2(t) = \frac{1}{222e^t}$.

For each $x, \bar{x} \in C_{\frac{1}{2}; \psi}(J)$ and $t \in J$, we have

$$|\Phi(x) - \Phi(\bar{x})| \leq \frac{1}{11} \|x - \bar{x}\|_{C_{\frac{1}{2}; \psi}},$$

and so the condition (Ax4) is satisfied with $\gamma = \frac{1}{11}$.

Also, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\mathcal{X}} &= \frac{\hat{\lambda}\gamma}{\Gamma_k(k\xi)} + \frac{q_2^* \hat{\lambda}}{(1 - q_3^*)\Gamma_k(\vartheta + k)} (\psi(b) - \psi(a))^{1 - \xi + \frac{\vartheta}{k}} \\ &= \frac{1}{11\sqrt{\pi}} + \frac{2}{(222e - 1)\sqrt{\pi}} \\ &\approx 0.0531629194375714 \\ &< 1. \end{aligned}$$

Then, the condition (4.2) of Theorem 4.4 is satisfied. Then the problem (5.1)-(5.2) has at least one solution in $C_{\frac{1}{2}; \psi}([1, e])$.

6. Conclusion

In this study, we introduced a novel generalized derivative operator known as the tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer fractional derivative. Alongside this, we thoroughly investigated and established the fundamental properties of this operator, taking into account the distinctive characteristics of the functions k -Gamma and k -Beta. Furthermore, we showcased the practicality and significance of our definitions by demonstrating the existence

and uniqueness of solutions to two tempered (k, ψ) -Hilfer problems. These problems involved nonlinear implicit fractional differential equations with nonlocal conditions. To prove the existence and uniqueness results, we employed the Banach contraction principle and Schaefer's fixed point theorem. Additionally, to illustrate the applicability of our main findings, we provided several concrete examples. These examples effectively highlighted the utility and generalizing nature of our proposed operator in various cases. Notably, the newly introduced operator serves as a versatile extension, encompassing previously defined fractional derivatives like the ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative found in the existing literature. This broader framework significantly enriches the current development of fractional calculus, opening up promising opportunities for future research in this dynamic and evolving field.

Declarations

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References

- [1] H. Afshari, E. Karapinar, A discussion on the existence of positive solutions of the boundary value problems via ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative on b -metric spaces. *Adv. Difference Equ.* 2020, Paper No. 616, 11 pp.
- [2] O. P. Agrawal, Some generalized fractional calculus operators and their applications in integral equations, *Frac. Cal. Appl. Anal.* **15** (4) (2012), 700-711.
- [3] A. Almalahi and K. Panchal, Existence results of ψ -Hilfer integro-differential equations with fractional order in Banach space, *Ann. Univ. Paedagog. Crac. Stud. Math.* **19** (2020), 171-192.
- [4] R. Almeida, M. L. Morgado, Analysis and numerical approximation of tempered fractional calculus of variations problems, *J. Comput. Appl. Math.* **361** (2019), 1-12.
- [5] M. Benchohra, E. Karapinar, J. E. Lazreg and A. Salim, *Advanced Topics in Fractional Differential Equations: A Fixed Point Approach*, Springer, Cham, 2023.
- [6] M. Benchohra, E. Karapinar, J. E. Lazreg and A. Salim, *Fractional Differential Equations: New Advancements for Generalized Fractional Derivatives*, Springer, Cham, 2023.
- [7] M. Bouaouid, Mild solutions of a class of conformable fractional differential equations with nonlocal conditions. *Acta Math. Appl. Sin. Engl. Ser.* **39** (2023), 249–261.
- [8] R. G. Buschman, Decomposition of an integral operator by use of Mikusinski calculus, *SIAM J. Math. Anal.* **3** (1972), 83-85.
- [9] L. Byszewski and V. Lakshmikantham, Theorem about the existence and uniqueness of a solution of a nonlocal abstract Cauchy problem in a Banach space, *Appl. Anal.* **40** (1990), 11-19.
- [10] Y. M. Chu, M. U. Awan, S. Talib, M. A. Noor and K. I. Noor, Generalizations of Hermite-Hadamard like inequalities involving χ_κ -Hilfer fractional integrals, *Adv. Difference Equ.* **2020** (2020), 594.
- [11] R. Diaz and C. Teruel, q, k -Generalized gamma and beta functions, *J. Nonlinear Math. Phys.* **12** (2005), 118-134.
- [12] T. A. Faree, S. K. Panchal, Existence of solution for impulsive fractional differential equations with nonlocal conditions by topological degree theory. *Results Appl. Math.* **18** (2023), 100377.
- [13] A. Granas and J. Dugundji, *Fixed Point Theory*, Springer-Verlag, New York, 2003.
- [14] R. Herrmann, *Fractional Calculus: An Introduction for Physicists*. Singapore: World Scientific Publishing Company, 2011.
- [15] R. Hilfer, *Applications of Fractional Calculus in Physics*, World Scientific, Singapore, 2000.
- [16] A. A. Kilbas, Hari M. Srivastava and Juan J. Trujillo, *Theory and Applications of Fractional Differential Equations*. North-Holland Mathematics Studies, 204. Elsevier Science B.V., Amsterdam, 2006.

- [17] S. Krim, A. Salim, S. Abbas and M. Benchohra, Functional k -generalized ψ -Hilfer fractional differential equations in b -metric spaces. *Pan-Amer. J. Math.* **2** (2023), 10 pages. <https://doi.org/10.28919/cpr-pajm/2-5>
- [18] S. Krim, A. Salim and M. Benchohra, On implicit Caputo tempered fractional boundary value problems with delay. *Lett. Nonlinear Anal. Appl.* **1** (1) (2023), 12-29. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7682064>
- [19] K. D. Kucche, A. D. Mali, A. Fernandez and H. M. Fahad, On tempered Hilfer fractional derivatives with respect to functions and the associated fractional differential equations, *Chaos, Solitons & Fractals.* **163** (2022), 112547.
- [20] C. Li, W. Deng and L. Zhao, Well-posedness and numerical algorithm for the tempered fractional differential equations, *Discr. Contin. Dyn. Syst. Ser. B.* **24** (2019), 1989-2015.
- [21] R. Luca and A. Tudorache, On a system of Hadamard fractional differential equations with nonlocal boundary conditions on an infinite interval. *Fractal Fract.* **7** (6) (2023), 458.
- [22] A. D. Mali, K. D. Kucche, A. Fernandez and H. M. Fahad, On tempered fractional calculus with respect to functions and the associated fractional differential equations, *Math Meth Appl Sci.* **45** (17) (2022), 11134-11157.
- [23] M. Medved and E. Brestovanska, Differential Equations with Tempered ψ -Caputo Fractional Derivative, *Math. Model. Anal.* **26** (2021), 631-650.
- [24] S. Mubeen and G. M. Habibullah, k -Fractional Integrals and Application, *Int. J. Contemp. Math. Sciences* **7** (2012), 89-94.
- [25] J. E. Nápoles Valdés, Generalized fractional Hilfer integral and derivative, *Contr. Math.* **2** (2020), 55–60.
- [26] N. A. Obeidat, D. E. Bentil, New theories and applications of tempered fractional differential equations, *Nonlinear Dyn.* **105** (2021), 1689-1702.
- [27] S. Rashid, M. Aslam Noor, K. Inayat Noor, Y. M. Chu, Ostrowski type inequalities in the sense of generalized \mathcal{K} -fractional integral operator for exponentially convex functions, *AIMS Math.* **5** (2020), 2629-2645.
- [28] F. Sabzikar, M. M. Meerschaert and J. Chen, Tempered fractional calculus, *J. Comput. Phys.* **293** (2015), 14-28.
- [29] A. Salim, M. Benchohra and J. E. Lazreg, Nonlocal k -generalized ψ -Hilfer impulsive initial value problem with retarded and advanced arguments, *Appl. Anal. Optim.* **6** (2022), 21-47.
- [30] A. Salim, M. Benchohra and J. E. Lazreg, On implicit k -generalized ψ -Hilfer fractional differential coupled systems with periodic conditions, *Qual. Theory Dyn. Syst.* **22** (2023), 46 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12346-023-00776-1>
- [31] A. Salim, M. Benchohra, J. E. Lazreg and J. Henderson, On k -generalized ψ -Hilfer boundary value problems with retardation and anticipation. *ATNA.* **6** (2022), 173-190. <https://doi.org/10.31197/atnaa.973992>
- [32] A. Salim, M. Benchohra, J. E. Lazreg and E. Karapinar, On k -generalized ψ -Hilfer impulsive boundary value problem with retarded and advanced arguments. *J. Math. Ext.* **15** (2021), 1-39. <https://doi.org/10.30495/JME.SI.2021.2187>
- [33] A. Salim, M. Benchohra, J. E. Lazreg and G. N'Guérékata, Existence and k -Mittag-Leffler-Ulam-Hyers stability results of k -generalized ψ -Hilfer boundary value problem. *Nonlinear Studies.* **29** (2022), 359–379.
- [34] A. Salim, M. Benchohra, J. E. Lazreg and Y. Zhou, On k -generalized ψ -Hilfer impulsive boundary value problem with retarded and advanced arguments in Banach spaces. *J. Nonl. Evol. Equ. Appl.* **2022** (2023), 105-126.
- [35] A. Salim, S. Bouriah, M. Benchohra, J. E. Lazreg and E. Karapinar, A study on k -generalized ψ -Hilfer fractional differential equations with periodic integral conditions. *Math. Methods Appl. Sci.* (2023), 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mma.9056>
- [36] A. Salim, J. E. Lazreg, B. Ahmad, M. Benchohra and J. J. Nieto, A study on k -generalized ψ -Hilfer derivative operator, *Vietnam J. Math.* (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10013-022-00561-8>
- [37] S.G. Samko, A.A. Kilbas and O.I. Marichev, *Fractional Integrals and Derivatives. Theory and Applications*, Gordon and Breach, Yverdon, 1993.
- [38] B. Shiri, G. Wu and D. Baleanu, Collocation methods for terminal value problems of tempered fractional differential equations, *Appl. Numer. Math.* **156** (2020), 385-395.
- [39] J. V. C. Sousa and E. Capelas de Oliveira, A Gronwall inequality and the Cauchy-type problem by means of ψ -Hilfer operator, *Differ. Equ. Appl.* **11** (2019), 87-106.
- [40] J. V. C. Sousa and E. Capelas de Oliveira, Fractional order pseudo-parabolic partial differential equation: Ulam-Hyers stability, *Bull. Braz. Math. Soc.* **50** (2019), 481-496.
- [41] J. V. C. Sousa and E. Capelas de Oliveira, On the ψ -Hilfer fractional derivative, *Commun. Nonlinear Sci. Numer. Simul.* **60** (2018), 72-91.
- [42] J. R. Wang, Y. R. Zhang, Nonlocal initial value problems for differential equations with Hilfer fractional derivative. *Appl. Math. Comput.* **266** (2015), 850-859.